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Research Article

**EVALUATION OF ANTI-OBESITY ACTIVITY OF AQUEOUS
EXTRACT OF *Trianthema portulacastrum* (Linn) WHOLE PLANT
PARTS ON MALE SPRAGUE–DAWLEY RATS****P.Seeta^{1*}, J.N.Suresh Kumar², B.Manasa³, Ch.China Mastan³, D.Jayasree³, P.Bi Fathima³
and K.Hari Naga Himaja³**¹Faculty, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences²Principal, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences³Research scholar, Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences**Abstract:**

*Obesity is a complex multifactorial disease that accumulated excess body fat leads to negative effects on health. Obesity continues to accelerate resulting in an unprecedented epidemic that shows no significant signs of slowing down any time soon. Raised body mass index (BMI) is a risk factor for non communicable diseases such as diabetes, cardiovascular diseases, and musculoskeletal disorders, resulting in dramatic decrease of life quality and expectancy. This study aims at investigating the effect of *Trianthema portulacastrum* (Linn) whole plant parts on high fat diet (HFD) induced obesity in male sprague–dawley rats. Thirty male Wistar rats were divided into five groups with six rats each. Apart from Group 1 (normal control which received normal pelleted diet), obesity was induced in 24 rats of Group 2 to 5 with HFD. Group 2, the obese control was administered with 100% HFD, group 2 is consider as a disease control group while the diet for group 3 and 5 was received with 30mg/kg orlistat, 100mg/kg and 200 mg/kg *Trianthema portulacastrum* extract respectively, from 21st day along with HFD. *Trianthema portulacastrum* had weight-loss effect in that it decreased body weight, food intake, and lipid levels.*

Keywords: obesity, epidemiology, pathophysiology, orlistat, bodyweights, blood sample, retro orbital puncture, lipids.

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INTRODUCTION:

Globally, increased weight and obesity are rising in both the developing and developed world. Over the past 20 years, the rate of obesity has tripled in developing countries as they become more urbanized and adopt a Western lifestyle of higher caloric intake combined with a more sedentary lifestyle. Obesity has become recognized as one of the major health problems threatening the world today, along with malnourishment, underweight, and infectious disease. The International Obesity Task Force and the World Health Organization (WHO) report over 1.1 billion adults worldwide are overweight, 312 million of whom are obese. In addition, over 155 million children are overweight or obese worldwide; 42 million of these children are under the age of 5. The areas of the world at greatest risk due to dramatic increases in prevalence rates are the Middle East, Pacific Islands, Southeast Asia, and China⁽¹⁾

The co-existence of obesity and under nutrition in developing countries is not uncommon. The lower-class population in low-income countries tends to be under weight and malnourished. On the other hand, the lower class population in middle-income countries has a high risk of obesity. Paradoxically, many poor families in these middle-income countries have obese parents with malnourished children. Some studies explain this phenomenon with the “thrifty gene” hypothesis, which states that intrauterine growth retardation and the resulting low birth weight confers a predisposition to obesity later in life.² Obesity is highly prevalent in the middle-income countries of Eastern Europe, Latin America, and Asia, where obesity is the fifth most common cause of disease burden, ranking just below underweight.⁽²⁾

A preliminary review of the prevalence of childhood obesity (1) indicated that the criteria used to assess obesity in children and adolescents varied widely. Therefore, it appeared essential to determine the most appropriate measurement with which to define obesity in children and adolescents for global use before the worldwide prevalence of childhood and adolescent obesity could be explored. As a result, the International Obesity Task Force (IOTF) convened a workshop on childhood obesity to explore the strengths and limitations of existing approaches to the measurement of childhood obesity. The workshop was held in Dublin on 16 June 1997 immediately before the European Congress on Obesity.

The workshop began with a review of the validity of the body mass index (BMI; in kg/m²) as a measure of

body fat and as an index of morbidity. Several factors were also considered that either contribute to the validity of the cutoff point used to define obesity or could modify or augment the definition of obesity. These factors included the effect of curve smoothing and transformations on the cutoff point, the likelihood that obesity will persist at various BMI cutpoints in childhood, and the contribution of visceral fat. The effect of obesity cutpoints, based on populations in the United States and United Kingdom, on prevalence was examined in several different populations to illustrate the importance of an international reference population to assess the prevalence of obesity. Because almost all the data considered at the workshop were derived from Europe or North America, validation studies in other populations are needed. Nonetheless, the articles included here and the consensus that emerged from the workshop provide a research agenda that will 1) significantly improve our understanding of the strengths and limitations of the measures used to define obesity, 2) define the characteristics of the populations required to develop an international reference population, and 3) help specify the research agenda necessary to validate the definition of obesity that we have proposed.⁽³⁾

PREVALENCE OF OBESITY: Obesity rates have been steadily increasing globally over the past few decades. According to the World Health Organization, over 650 million adults were classified as obese in 2016. The rising prevalence is alarming and poses significant public health challenges.

Causes of obesity³

At individual level, the combination of excessive food energy intake and lack of physical activity is thought to explain most of obesity causes. In limited cases, obesity is due to genetic factors, medical reasons, or psychiatric illness. On the other hand, increasing rates of obesity at a societal level are felt to be due to easily accessible and palatable diet, increased reliance on cars, and mechanized manufacturing. A 2006 review identified ten other possible contributors to the recent increase of obesity including insufficient sleep, endocrine disruptors, decreased variability in ambient temperature, decreased rates of smoking, as smoking suppresses appetite, increased use of medications that can cause weight gain (e.g., atypical antipsychotics), proportional increases in ethnic and age groups that tend to be heavier, pregnancy at a later age (which may cause susceptibility to obesity in children), epigenetic risk factors passed on generationally,

natural selection for higher BMI, and assortative mating leading to increased concentration of obesity risk factors.

Diet

Obesity rates in the US (1971–2000) increased from 14.5% to 30.9%.²⁴ During the same period, there was an increase in the average amount of food consumed (average increase for women 335 and 168 cal./day). Most of this extra food energy was due to the increase in carbohydrates rather than fat consumption.⁴

Sedentary lifestyle

There is a large shift toward less physically demanding work worldwide. Currently, at least 60% of the world's population gets insufficient exercise, due to increased use of mechanized transportation and a greater prevalence of labor-saving technology at home. The WHO indicates people worldwide are taking up less active recreational pursuits. In both children and adults, there is an association between television viewing time and the risk of obesity.

Genetics

Like many other medical conditions, obesity is the result of interplay between genetic and environmental factors. Polymorphisms in various genes controlling appetite and metabolism predispose to obesity when sufficient food energy is present. People with two copies of the FTO gene (fat mass and obesity associated gene) have been found on average to weigh 3–4 kg more and have a 1.67 fold greater risk of obesity compared to those without the risk allele.

Medical and psychiatric illness

Certain physical and mental illnesses and medications used to treat them can increase the risk of obesity. Medical illnesses that increase obesity risk include several rare genetic syndrome (Cohen syndrome), as well as some congenital or acquired conditions: hypothyroidism, growth hormone deficiency, and eating disorders (binge eating disorder and night eating syndrome). The risk of overweight and obesity is higher in patients with psychiatric disorders than in persons without psychiatric disorders.⁵

Social determinants

Genetic influences are important to understand obesity. They cannot explain the current dramatic increase in obesity. Though, excess energy

consumption than energy expenditure leads to obesity on individual basis. In developing countries women of a high social class were less likely to be obese. Those who quit smoking will gain an average of 4.4 kg (men) and 5.0 kg (women) over ten years. However, changing rates of smoking have little effect on the overall rates of obesity.

Infectious agents

The study of infectious agent's effect on metabolism is still in its early stages. The gut flora in obese and lean individuals can affect the metabolic potential. This apparent alteration is believed to confer a greater capacity to gain energy contributing to obesity. An association between viruses and obesity has been found in humans and several different animal species.⁶

SYMPTOMS OF OBESITY IN ADULTS

The American Medical Association considers obesity itself a disease that needs to be diagnosed and treated. That's due to symptoms and complications that are common among people with obesity.

Common symptoms of obesity in adults include:

- Excess body fat, particularly around the waist
- Shortness of breath
- Sweating more than usual
- Snoring
- Trouble sleeping
- Skin problems from moisture accumulating in the folds
- Inability to perform simple physical tasks you could easily perform before weight gain
- Fatigue, which can range from mild to extreme
- Pain, especially in the back and joints
- Psychological issues such as negative self-esteem, depression, shame, and social isolation.

SYMPTOMS OF OBESITY IN CHILDREN

The CDC says the rate of childhood obesity in the U.S. has tripled in the last 50 years.⁶ In 2020, nearly 20% of American children and adolescents (ages 2 to 19) were considered to have obesity.⁷

Common childhood obesity symptoms may include:⁸

- Fatty tissue deposits (may be noticeable in the breast area)
- Stretch marks on the hips and back
- Acanthosis nigricans (dark velvety skin around the neck and other areas)
- Shortness of breath with physical activity
- Sleep apnea
- Constipation
- Gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD)
- Low self-esteem
- Early puberty in biological females/delayed puberty in biological males
- Orthopedic problems, such as flat feet or dislocated hips¹⁰

RISK FACTORS FOR OVER WEIGHT AND OBESITY:

- Type 2 diabetes¹¹
- High blood pressure
- Heart disease
- Stroke
- Metabolic syndrome
- Fatty liver disease
- Some cancers
- Breathing problem
- Osteoarthritis
- Gout
- Disease of the gallbladder and pancreas
- Kidney diseases
- Pregnancy problems
- Fertility problems
- Sexual function problems
- Mental health problems

Type 2 diabetes

Type 2 diabetes is a disease that occurs when your blood glucose, also called blood sugar, is too high. Nearly 9 in 10 people with type 2 diabetes have overweight or obesity.¹² Overtime, high blood glucose can lead to heart disease, stroke, kidney disease eye problem, nerve damage and other health problems.

High blood pressure

Overweight and obesity may raise your risk for high blood pressure. High blood pressure also called hypertension, is a condition in which blood flows through your blood vessels with a force greater than normal. High blood pressure can strain your heart,

damage blood vessels, and raise your risk of Heart attack, stroke, Kidney disease, and death.

Heart Disease

Heart disease is a term used to describe several health problems that affect your heart, such as a heart attack, angina or an abnormal heart rhythm. Having overweight or obesity increases your risk of developing conditions that can lead to heart disease, such as high blood pressure, high blood cholesterol and high blood glucose.

Metabolic syndrome

Metabolic syndrome is a group of conditions that increase your risk for heart disease, diabetes, and stroke. To be diagnosed with metabolic syndrome, you must have at least three of the following conditions

- Large waist size
- high level of triglycerides in your blood
- high blood pressure
- high level of blood glucose when fasting
- low level of HDL cholesterol —the “good” cholesterol—in your blood.¹³

Fatty liver diseases

Fatty liver diseases develop when fat builds up in your liver, which can lead to severe liver damage, cirrhosis, or even liver failure. These diseases include nonalcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and nonalcoholic steatohepatitis (NASH). NAFLD and NASH most often affect people who have overweight or obesity.

Some cancers

Cancer is a collection of related diseases. In all types of cancer, some of the body’s cells begin to grow abnormally or out of control. The cancerous cells sometimes spread to other parts of the body.

Osteoarthritis

Osteoarthritis^{NIH} is a common, long-lasting health problem that causes pain, swelling, stiffness, and reduced motion in your joints. Obesity is a leading risk factor for osteoarthritis in the knees, hips, and ankles.

Having overweight or obesity may raise your risk of getting osteoarthritis by putting extra pressure on your joints and cartilage. If you have excess body fat, your blood may have higher levels of substances that cause inflammation. Inflamed joints may raise your risk for osteoarthritis.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Animals

Healthy male Spragu-Dawley rats were kept in neat & clean polypropylene cages (3 rats in each cage) & maintained under controlled conditions of room temperature ($22 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) and humidity ($55 \pm 5\%$) with

12 hours of each light & dark cycle. All the rats were given normal pellet diet along with water ad libitum before dietary manipulation. Entire study was performed according to guidelines prescribed by the Committee for Control & Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CCSEA). The protocol for study was approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of Institute bearing protocol number 1414 / A /11 /CCSEA / NIPS / IAEC / 2025 / 001.

Male SD rats weighing about 220- 250 gm were selected for study. They were given a cafeteria diet for the period of 6 weeks for inducing obesity.

Table-1: Components of Cafeteria Diet with their Calorie value

S.No	Components	Calorie value(kcal/100g)
1.	Dried coconut Biscuits	600
2.	Biscuit	360
3.	Condensed milk	335
4.	Chocolate	550
5.	Bread	230
6.	Boiled potato	80

EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Total 30 rats were divided into 5 groups of six rats in each group.

Group-I : Normal Control rats were given standard chowdiet and water ad libitum for 42 days (6 weeks).

Group-II: Obese control rats were fed only cafeteria diet for 42days (6weeks) for induction of obesity.

Group III: Received HFD for 42 days along with 30mg/kg orlistat from the 21st day for next 20 days.

Group IV: Received HFD for 42 days along with 100mg/kg TPPE from the 21st day for next 20 days.

Group V: Received HFD for 42 days along with 200mg/kg TPPE from the 21st day for next 20 days.

Fig-1: Normal control

Fig-2: Disease control(DC)

Fig-3: Standard group

Fig-4: TPPE-100mg

Fig-5: TPPE-200mg

Parameters evaluated

Measurement of Bodyweight

Body weight of individual animals was taken every day by using digital weighing balance for 6 weeks. The % change in bodyweight produced by standard drug & test extracts with respect to normal diet and high fat diet control rats was calculated.

Measurement of Food intake

Food intake of each group of animals was determined initially and then every week upto 6 weeks by measuring the difference between the pre weighed chows and weight of the food that remained after 24 h. by using digital weighing balance.⁽¹¹⁾

Method used for Lipid Profile

- Lipid profile analysis of all experimental animals was carried out on last day (42 Day) of the study. Obese control group fed with only cafeteria diet for all 6 weeks.
- Elevated levels of triglycerides (TG), low density lipoprotein (LDL), significantly lowered levels of high-density-lipoprotein (HDL) as compared to normal control group rats as well as all treatment group animals.
- TPPE (100 mg/kg) & TPPE (200 mg/kg) treatments for last 6 weeks significantly lowered the levels of TG, VLDL, LDL.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:**Table-2:** Effect of oral administration of TPPE on weekly body weight gain of HFD- induced obese rats

GROUPS	BodyWeight(gm)			
	Week-1	Week-2	Week-3	Week-4
NC	234±5.72	258±6.17	267±3.95	275.18±4.68
DC	232±4.92	317±3.27	352±4.38	371.53±340
Orlistat(30 mg/kg)	235±8.05	321±4.76	310±7.16	278.68 ±2.51
TPPE(100mg/kg)	236±3.12	318±5.33	304±6.37	291.70 ±3.72
TPPE(200mg/kg)	234±2.83	312±6.93	297±5.98	283.47 ±2.47

WEIGHT VARIATION GRAPH

Fig-6 : Weight Variation Graph

Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM, n=6.

Table-3 : Effects of TPPE on Body Weight

Groups	AverageBodyWeight (gm) (Last Day)	% Reduction inbodyweight
NC	275.18 ± 4.68	---
DC	371.53 ± 3.40	---
Orlistat(30mg/kg)	278.68 ± 2.51	24.99%
TPPE(100mg/kg)	291.70 ± 3.72	21.48%
TPPE(200mg/kg)	283.47 ± 2.47	23.70%

Formula for % reduction in bodyweight= $\frac{\text{currentweight}-\text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$

AVERAGE BODY WEIGHTS

Fig-7: Average Body Weights Graph

Values indicates amount of food intake by a group of six rats per day in gm.

Table-4 :Effects of TPPE on daily food intake

GROUPS	Food Consumption(gm)			
	Week-1	Week-2	Week-3	Week-4
NC	130.8	131.2	138.1	138.6
DC	162.1	171.5	168.2	164.9
Orlistat(30mg/kg)	132.8	122.4	114.9	106.5
TPPE(100mg/kg)	140.4	130.3	126.2	126.2
TPPE(200mg/kg)	133.7	121.4	107.1	107.1

Table-5:Effects of TPPE on average daily food intake

Groups	Average Daily Food intake (gm/group)
NC	133.48 ± 0.55
DC	162.64 ± 2.50
Orlistat(30mg/kg)	124.91 ± 1.43
TPPE(100mg/kg)	131.01 ± 1.27
TPPE(200mg/kg)	126.37 ± 1.57

LIPIDPROFILE:

Table-6 :Effect of TPPE on Lipid content on 42ndday

Groups	TG	HDL	LDL
NC	53.37	52.90	43.15
DC	173.25	35.10	96.29
Orlistat	80.28	63.18	51.94
TPPE(100mg/kg)	87.81	52.35	57.07
TPPE(200mg/kg)	77.84	75.26	49.40

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

- Obesity is a cosmetic disorder described as proximal or excessive fat accumulation in adipose tissue along with major vital organs like heart, liver & skeletal muscles. It is considered as a significant hazard factor to the wellbeing and prosperity of human beings.
- In majority of cases drug treatment of obesity is related with bounce back weight increase after the suspension of medication admission, adverse effects caused by medicine and potential for sedate maltreatment
- The present study was aimed to investigate the potential anti-obesity activity of aqueous extracts of a whole plant of TPPE along with their phytochemical analysis.
- The whole plant of TPPE L was collected from botanical garden of Narasaraopeta Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences and evaluated according to Ayurvedic Pharmacopoeia of India.
- Pharmacognostical and physicochemical parameters assured the authenticity, quality and purity of crude drug. The aqueous extracts of plant material was prepared and subjected soxhlet extraction by using distilled water as a solvent. The preliminary qualitative tests showed the presence of various constituents mainly saponins, phenolic compounds, flavonoids, phytosterols, alkaloids in the extract.
- Cafeteria diet was provided to rats to induce obesity for 6 weeks and treatment by standard drug orlistat and TPPE started by the end of 3 week along with cafeteria diet. Results obtained in our experiment indicated that rats fed with only cafeteria diet for 6 weeks provoked significant increase in body weight gain, food consumption.
- TPPE treatment for last 3 weeks resulted in significant reduction in body weight gain, food consumption was compared with standard drug Orlistat.
- Further studies will be needed for the human use.

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